

Better welfare for broiler chickens given more types of environmental enrichments and more space to enjoy them

Judit Vas^{a,*}, Neila BenSassi^b, Guro Vasdal^c, Ruth C. Newberry^a

^a Norwegian University of Life Sciences, Faculty of Biosciences, Department of Animal and Aquacultural Sciences, P. O. Box 5003, 1432 Ås, Norway

^b Neiker-Tecnalia, Campus Agroalimentario de Arkaute, Apto 46, E-01080 Vitoria-Gasteiz, Spain

^c Norwegian Meat and Poultry Research Centre, Lørenveien 38, PO Box 396, Økern, 0513 Oslo, Norway

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Broiler chicken
Environmental enrichment
Environmental complexity
Space allowance
Positive welfare
Behaviour

ABSTRACT

Providing an increased variety of environmental enrichment options, with sufficient space to use them, could increase the behavioural expression of positive affective states in production animals. The goal of this study was to investigate associations between the number of different environmental enrichment options provided by commercial broiler chicken producers at different stocking densities and behavioural indicators of positive affective states in chickens. Thirty fast-growing commercial broiler chicken flocks with various numbers of environmental enrichment types (range: 0–4; e.g. compressed wood shavings bales, cardboard boxes, plastic crates, peat, perches, windows providing natural light) and space allowances (range: 0.058–0.076 m²/bird) were observed at approximately 28 days of age, when stocking density averaged 23.4 kg/m². A practical transect sampling method involving 15-s 1–0 scans of successive “patches” along transects between feeders and drinkers and along the wall was used to record spontaneous occurrences of easily detected elements of play (worm-run, play-fight, wing flap, jump, run), inquisitive exploratory behaviour (ground-scratch) and comfort behaviour (vertical wing shake, as a marker of dustbathing) performed by undisturbed chickens. When summed together, these behaviours were performed by an average of 1% of the estimated number of chickens observed during the scans. There were positive associations between environmental complexity (number of environmental enrichment types provided) and the prevalence of play-fighting, ground-scratching, vertical wing shaking, and the sum of all observed behaviours. Farmers providing more types of enrichment also tended to provide more space per bird. After taking the number of enrichment types into account, providing more space per bird was associated with higher levels of jumping, running, and the sum of observed behaviours, though a lower prevalence of vertical wing shaking. In conclusion, an increased diversity of environmental enrichment types in commercial broiler houses was associated with higher expression of behavioural indicators of positive affect including social play, curiosity-driven inquisitive exploration, and comfort behaviour, while higher space allowances facilitated the expression of space-demanding locomotory play.

1. Introduction

While it is unrealistic to expect that a conscious animal's life can be completely free of negative experiences, we can aim to provide managed animals with a ‘life worth living’ or a ‘good life’ (FAWC, 2009) by offering opportunities for positive experiences. The term ‘quality of life’ refers to “the balance between pleasant and unpleasant affect in one's life over time” (McMillan, 2000). It implies that we can aim for a high level of welfare (or quality of life) in managed animals not only by reducing negative affective states but also by promoting hedonically positive affective states, thereby contributing to long-term happiness

(Webb et al., 2019). One means of stimulating positive affective states could be to provide animals with environmental enrichment. Environmental enrichment has been defined as the provision of biologically relevant modifications to the environment of managed animals that lead to functional benefits in the short or long term (Newberry, 1995). These modifications include provision of various substrates and structures that add environmental complexity relative to an unenriched (barren) environment by giving animals varied opportunities to engage in species-relevant behaviours (Vasdal et al., 2019).

Play, exploratory and comfort behaviours can indicate positive affect in animals, contributing to the positive side of the welfare spectrum

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: judit.vas@nmbu.no (J. Vas).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2023.105901>

Received 28 October 2022; Received in revised form 8 March 2023; Accepted 15 March 2023

Available online 17 March 2023

0168-1591/© 2023 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

(Boissy et al., 2007). Play is involved in the development of kinematic and emotional skills that enhance plasticity to cope with future events (Himmler et al., 2013; Špinka et al., 2001). It is displayed in a repetitive but non-stereotypic manner and can serve as positive reinforcement (Burghardt, 2014). Play incorporates elements resembling those occurring in other contexts but is performed in a manner that appears non-serious due to exaggerated movements, self-handicapping and spontaneity, giving the overall impression that the participants are having fun (Špinka et al., 2001). Exploratory behaviour can range from inspection of novel and potentially dangerous stimuli to inquisitive exploration (Berlyne, 1960). While inspection may evoke both curiosity and fear and is, therefore, not solely positive (Boissy et al., 2007), inquisitive exploration, such as the relaxed, non-nutritive foraging behaviour of well-fed animals is more purely associated with curiosity-motivated positive affect that functions to develop knowledge about resources that may be exploited now or in the future. Comfort behaviour includes bathing, grooming, scratching and stretching activities that are assumed to be self-rewarding due to their functional relevance for body care (Boissy et al., 2007). Play, inquisitive exploration and comfort behaviours usually occur in situations when current basic needs of animals are satisfied, there is no immediate or urgent threat to life, and animals are in a relaxed state (Berlyne, 1960; Špinka et al., 2001). Under these conditions, these behaviours can be viewed as having functional benefits in the longer term (i.e. indicative of an enrichment effect) while also indicating positive affect in the immediate instances when they appear.

Until recently (Baxter et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2020; Rayner et al., 2020; Lundén et al., 2022), play behaviour in chickens has been a relatively neglected area of study. Worm-running (also referred to as food-running) is often performed in a non-nutritive context by young chickens, when it is unrelated to the establishment of social rank and fits criteria for object play (Cloutier et al., 2004). Play-fighting (also referred to as sparring or social play) occurs at an age when agonistic interactions are rare (Bailie et al., 2013; Dennis et al., 2008; Fortomaris et al., 2007). The typical absence of physical contact, lack of clear directionality in outcome of encounters, and lack of association with neediness for resources such as feed or water are consistent with a playful rather than aggressive motivational state (Hall, 2001). Spontaneous wing flapping, jumping, and running (also referred to as frolicking) are locomotory play elements in young chickens. Their link to functional benefits and positive affect is indicated by their association with stronger bones (e.g. Knowles and Broom, 1990; Nørgaard-Nielsen, 1990), release from spatial restriction (Baxter et al., 2019; Nicol, 1987), and anticipation of positive events (Zimmerman et al., 2011).

Foraging by chickens comprises both ground-pecking and ground-scratching, with the latter being less common but more noticeable and easily quantified. Ground-scratching uncovers and reveals diverse materials, facilitating the discovery of edible items. It serves as a key element of curiosity-motivated inquisitive exploratory behaviour and its prevalence can thus be considered an indicator of the extent to which chickens find their litter enjoyable to explore.

Dustbathing is an important form of comfort behaviour in chickens, serving to remove stale feather lipids (van Liere, 1991; 1992), as well as having anti-parasitic (Vezzoli et al., 2015) and thermoregulatory functions (Duncan et al., 1998). Chickens have a preference for dustbathing in a relatively fine particulate material such as peat, which is functionally more effective as a dustbathing substrate than commonly supplied coarser litter materials such as wood shavings (Olsson and Keeling, 2005). Dustbathing may contribute to skeletal health in broilers (Vestergaard and Sanotra, 1999), and has been proposed to indicate a state of pleasure (Widowski and Duncan, 2000). Hens give reward calls when anticipating access to a dustbathing substrate (McGrath et al., 2017). Vertical wing shaking is the most visible element in a dustbathing sequence, and has been used as a marker of dustbathing in multiple studies (e.g. de Jong et al., 2007; Holt et al., 2023; Shields et al., 2004).

Most studies reporting on environmental complexity for broiler

chickens have compared a single type of enrichment, or a standardised set of enrichments, versus no enrichment (e.g. Anderson et al., 2021; Bach et al., 2019; Bizeray et al., 2002; de Jong et al., 2021). It is unclear how increasing the number of different enrichment types, reflecting increasing levels of environmental complexity, influences the expression of behavioural indicators of positive affect. This is an important consideration in commercial broiler production because the economic cost of providing enrichments (Jones et al., 2020), as well as concerns about biosecurity, food safety, occupational safety, and environmental sustainability, place constraints on their use in practice. Furthermore, the relatively high stocking densities found under commercial conditions are likely to restrict opportunities for chickens to access enrichments, thereby affecting the ability of chickens to benefit from them (Riber et al., 2018).

In Norway, a period in which broiler chicken farmers were experimenting with providing different commercially feasible enrichments gave us an opportunity to investigate how the number of different types of enrichments impacted the expression of behavioural indicators of positive affect in fast-growing commercial flocks (average growth rate >50 g/day). There was also variation in the space allowance per bird across the flocks. We have previously reported that higher numbers of enrichment types and greater space allowances were associated with fewer indicators of negative welfare (BenSassi et al., 2019a). Here, we focus on the positive side of the welfare equation. We hypothesized that provision of more types of environmental enrichments would stimulate higher levels of behaviours associated with positive affect, especially under relatively spacious conditions. Specifically, we predicted higher levels of play (worm-running, play-fighting, wing flapping, jumping, running), inquisitive exploratory behaviour (ground scratching), comfort behaviour (vertical wing shaking) and the sum of these behaviours with higher numbers of enrichment types. Further, we predicted that additional space per bird would facilitate the performance of these behaviours and especially the most space-demanding ones such as running. Given that responses to enrichments may be masked by human disturbance, we present results on the spontaneous behaviour performed by undisturbed birds.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Animals, housing, and management

Farm participation in the study was voluntary. We observed 30 flocks of Ross 308, mixed sex chickens, all hatched at the same hatchery. The Ross 308 is the most commonly grown broiler chicken hybrid worldwide, and its temperament is influenced by selection for rapid growth and high feed efficiency (Aviagen, 2022). The chickens were raised on 15 commercial farms in eastern Norway having membership in the agricultural cooperative Nortura. We visited two successive flocks per farm, both in the same house, as close as possible to a flock age of 28 days (mean±SE age: 27.9 ± 0.2, range: 26–31 days, with mean±SE stocking density: 23.4 ± 0.6 kg/m², range: 18.1–29.6 kg/m²). The two flocks per farm varied in the number and combination of environmental enrichment types offered, with from 0 to 4 of the following types being registered per flock: wood shavings bales, peat moss, cardboard boxes, two different types of plastic crates, windows, perches, and pyramids of boxes (described in Supplementary Material Table S1). The houses had a mean (± SE) floor area of 1308 ± 79 m² (range: 700–2050 m²), holding flocks of 19,387 ± 950 chickens (range: 9335–34,657) with a space allowance of 0.067 ± 0.001 m²/bird (range: 0.058–0.076) on the day of the visit.

The well-insulated houses were equipped with mechanical ventilation and whole-house heating. The photoperiod was gradually reduced to 16–18 h by one week of age. Fresh litter (typically wood shavings) was supplied on the concrete floor after thorough cleaning before each flock. Feed and water were provided ad libitum. Farmers checked the chickens at least twice a day, and removed any seriously ill, injured, or

dead chickens. Flocks were slaughtered at 32–35 days of age.

2.2. Data collection

The houses were divided into rows by the feeding and drinking lines, forming 7–11 transects (BenSassi et al., 2018, 2019b; Marchewka et al., 2013, 2015). We sampled behaviour in successive “observation patches” along the transects. Patch length was denoted by the distance between the centres of the outer two feed pans in each set of three adjacent round feed pans, and patch width was defined as the width of the transect (i.e. between adjacent feeder and drinker lines, or between the wall of the house and the adjacent feeder or drinker line). To sample from representative undisturbed areas of each house, we collected data from a total of approximately 96 patches, located in three (houses with 7 transects), four (houses with 8 transects), five (houses with 9 transects) or six (houses with 10 or 11 transects) adjacent transects. We started by observing patches in the 5th (houses with 7–10 transects) or 6th (houses with 11 transects) transect from the left wall (relative to the house entrance door at one end of the house) and finished with the transect along the right wall. In each transect, observations began at the third patch from the end of the house closest to the entrance door, avoiding any potentially unsettled birds near the door. We observed 16–24 patches/transect, depending on the number of transects/house, with a comparable ratio of observed patches in central (i.e. non-wall) transects and wall transects irrespective of the size and shape of the house.

The data were collected by three experienced observers. We had practiced the method together during a 1.5-h on-farm training session in which simultaneous scoring of the same chickens and immediate comparison of results allowed us to resolve discrepancies and simultaneous scoring of the same chickens and immediate comparison of results allowed us to resolve discrepancies and achieve a high level of agreement. To further control for any observer bias, each flock had two observers, who alternated between data collection in successive transects according to a pre-determined plan. The same two observers conducted the observations of 29 of the 30 flocks, and the third served as a backup on one occasion. We waited about 2 min after entering the house before commencing behavioural observations to allow birds to settle after initial arousal stimulated by our arrival. This was indicated by seeing that most of the birds were lying down again, the vocalisation level had returned to a low level, and birds had returned to the area around the entrance door. We were quiet during data collection and moved slowly with minimal upper body movement.

Data collection lasted about 1–1.5 h/flock. To avoid disturbing chickens in the observed patches, we sampled patches located two transects across from our current location (approximately 4.5 m away). Using a timer marking 15-s intervals, each observation patch was observed for 15 s, which allowed for a quick but thorough scan of chickens in the patch. During the next 15 s, we recorded the observed behaviour on a record sheet and then moved slowly forward to a position opposite the next (adjacent) patch, and so on, zigzagging up and down successive transects until all patches in the sampling plan had been observed.

The ethogram (Table 1) comprised energetic behaviours reflecting positive affective states that were expected to occur infrequently and to be highly visible. During each 15-s scan of an observation patch, we recorded the number of birds performing each behaviour in the ethogram. If the same chicken expressed more than one behaviour during the scan, the behaviour listed highest in Table 1 was recorded, thereby ensuring that each chicken was counted only once. Most of the behavioural time budget of Ross 308 chickens around 4 weeks of age is taken up by lying with the sternum on the litter and standing at feeders (e.g. Baxter et al., 2021; Bergmann et al., 2017; de Jong et al., 2021; Meyer et al., 2020), so it was easy to quickly spot and count birds performing the distinctive behaviours in our ethogram within the limited area of an observation patch. Because scans lasted only 15 s, we were able to keep track of these birds and avoid resampling them during the same scan.

Table 1

Ethogram of play, exploratory and comfort behaviours used as indicators of positive affect.^a

Behaviour	Description
Worm-run	Walking or running while carrying a small object projecting from the beak, such as a large wood shaving, piece of peat, or feather. The bird makes rapid changes of direction and attracts other birds to follow and attempt to grab the item. Only the bird carrying the object is counted as worm-running.
Play-fight	The bird runs or jumps directly towards the head of another standing bird, stops and stares. If the other bird does not respond, one bird is counted as play-fighting. If both birds face each other and stare while in close proximity, both birds are counted.
Wing flap	While active in an upright posture (i.e. not lying down), the bird raises and rapidly lowers both wings simultaneously, usually several times in rapid succession. Does not include slow stretching of wings, holding wings out but not flapping, or body shaking.
Jump	While active in an upright posture (i.e. not lying down), the bird jumps so both feet are off the substrate simultaneously; may jump up off the floor (e.g. up into the air or onto a box) or down from an elevated location onto the floor (e.g. off a box).
Run	While active in an upright posture (i.e. not lying down), the bird takes at least three rapid steps forward with one foot after the other, with both feet briefly lifted off the substrate during each stride, resulting in moving the body rapidly from one location to another.
Ground-scratch	While active in an upright posture (i.e. not lying down), the bird rakes the substrate with the toes and claws using a rapid backward kicking movement of the leg and foot. Often repeated with alternating feet.
Vertical wing shake	While dustbathing in a recumbent position with fluffed feathers, the bird simultaneously and rapidly lifts its wings up and down multiple times, often accompanied by leg movements; wings are held close to the body, scooping loose substrate material up into the feathers.

^a If more than one behaviour is performed during a 15-s scan, the behaviour highest in the table is recorded.

While it was possible for a bird to move between patches, potentially resulting in resampling of the same bird in subsequent scans, the likelihood was low because the observed behaviours occurred in brief bouts and other birds served as obstacles to extensive locomotion. Undisturbed 4-week-old broilers have been reported to move a summed net distance/min of about 0.4 ± 0.1 m/4 min (Meyer et al., 2020) or a net distance of about 0.5 ± 0.1 m/5 min (Leone and Estevez, 2008), supporting generally low travel distances at this age.

After completing the behavioural observations, we noted the types of enrichments provided (Fig. 1; Supplementary Material Table S1). We measured the interior dimensions of the house (length and width) using a laser measuring tool and determined the current flock size based on farm mortality records. We defined environmental complexity by the number of types of environmental enrichments present (Supplementary Material Table S2) and calculated the space allowance as house area/flock size on the day of visit. To establish patch areas, we measured the width of each observed transect and sampled distances between feed pans. The mean patch area was 3.4 ± 0.0 m². The summed area of observation patches was 317.7 ± 10.0 m²/house (range: 205–400 m²), which equalled $25.1 \pm 0.8\%$ of the total house area (range: 16.0–30.7%). Based on flock size on the day of visit, an estimated 4745 \pm 170 birds/flock were observed (range: 2736–6830), with an average of 51 ± 0.2 birds/patch, assuming even distribution of birds throughout the house.

2.3. Statistical analyses

Analyses were conducted using R (version 3.6.1, R Core Team, 2022), starting with Spearman correlations between the observed behaviours. We used generalized linear mixed models with binomial distribution to investigate how the flock prevalence of each observed

Fig. 1. Examples of the most common environmental enrichment types found in the commercial broiler houses: (a) cardboard box (b) plastic crate (c) peat (d) half of compressed wood shavings bale (photos: Judit Vas).

behavioural indicator of positive affect varied depending on variation between flocks in environmental complexity (the number of enrichment types provided, ranging from 0–4, treated as a continuous variable) and space allowance. The outcome variables were calculated as the number of birds observed performing each behaviour per flock (summed over all observed patches), and the total number per flock performing any of the behaviours in the ethogram (‘sum of observed behaviours’), expressed as a proportion of the estimated total birds observed per. The space allowance (m²/chicken) was correlated with environmental complexity (Spearman’s correlation, Rho=0.56, P = 0.012). Therefore, we regressed the space allowance against environmental complexity and used the residuals to represent space allowance in the model. Because two successive flocks in the same house were observed per farm, farm was included as a random factor in the model. Worm-running was too rare for analysis by itself but contributed to the sum of observed behaviours. Model fit was examined using the DHARMA package diagnostics.

3. Results

3.1. Descriptive statistics

The overall sum of chickens engaging in the observed behavioural indicators of positive affect accounted for 1.00% of the estimated total chickens observed (Fig. 2a). ‘Wing flap’ was recorded in all the observed flocks and was the most frequently recorded behaviour (47.14% of the recorded behavioural events, Fig. 2b). ‘Worm-run’ was the rarest behaviour, being recorded in only two of the 30 observed flocks.

Significant correlations occurred between four of the 15 possible

pairs of behaviours recorded (Table 2). Running often occurred together with wing flapping, sometimes leading to play-fights. Jumping was more likely to be seen when running occurred, and the litter-directed behaviours, ground-scratching and vertical wing shaking, also co-occurred more often than expected by chance.

Table 2
Spearman rank correlations between observed behaviours^a.

		Play-fight	Wing flap	Jump	Run	Ground-scratch	Vertical wing shake
Play-fight	Rho		0.47	-0.05	0.21	0.24	0.19
	P		**	NS	NS	NS	NS
Wing flap	Rho			0.02	0.53	0.07	0.17
	P			NS	**	NS	NS
Jump	Rho				0.58	0.02	-0.16
	P				***	NS	NS
Run	Rho					0.10	0.12
	P					NS	NS
Ground-scratch	Rho						0.38
	P						*
Vertical wing shake	Rho						
	P						

^a NS: P > 0.05, *: P < 0.05, **: P < 0.01, ***: P < 0.001. Under the diagonal, pale green background: Rho 0.2–0.35 (and P > 0.05); dark green background: Rho 0.35–0.6 (and P < 0.05).

Fig. 2. Mean±SE number of chickens engaging in different behavioural indicators of positive affect (a) as a % of estimated total chickens observed, and (b) as a % of total chickens performing the indicator behaviours.

3.2. Associations with environmental complexity and space allowance

Play-fighting increased with increasing environmental complexity (Fig. 3; Table 3) but was not associated with space allowance. Wing flapping was not specifically associated with either environmental complexity or space allowance. More jumping and running were observed in flocks with more space (Fig. 4) but these behaviours were not associated with environmental complexity. More ground-scratching was observed in flocks with higher environmental complexity irrespective of space provision (Fig. 5a). Vertical wing shakes were observed more frequently in flocks with increased environmental complexity (Fig. 5b), but less frequently in flocks with more space per bird (Table 3). Overall, the sum of observed behaviours was positively associated with both environmental complexity and the space allowance per bird (Table 3).

4. Discussion

4.1. Associations with environmental complexity

We hypothesised that greater environmental complexity and higher space allowances would generally increase positive affect among undisturbed chickens, resulting in a higher prevalence of the specific behaviours measured as indicators of positive affect and their overall sum. In the case of environmental complexity, our hypothesis was supported by the results on play-fighting, ground-scratching, vertical wing shaking, and the sum of observed behaviours.

Compared to more barren environmental conditions, increased environmental complexity may have stimulated spontaneous play through exposure to varied materials, elevations, and sensory stimuli providing opportunities for positive affective engagement (Lawrence et al., 2019). Proximity to structures that could serve as refuges for perching and hiding also likely played a role given that the play is expected under relatively safe environmental conditions (Špinková et al., 2001) and is suppressed in contexts associated with danger (Siviy et al., 2006; Vanderschuren et al., 1995). These explanations could account for the higher levels of play-fighting with increased environmental complexity, though do not elucidate why all forms of play were not similarly affected. This finding was probably related to our methodology, since we recorded a single behaviour per bird per scan, with play-fighting being recorded when other behaviours lower in the ethogram were also being performed by the same bird. The Spearman correlations show that, at the group level, play-fighting often co-occurred with wing flapping, which in turn was often performed along with jumping and running, suggesting that all these forms of play may have

Fig. 3. Association between environmental complexity (number of enrichment types) and occurrence of play-fights (values predicted from the model).

Table 3

Associations of environmental complexity (number of enrichment types) and space allowance with the recorded behaviours.

Behaviour	Environmental complexity		Space allowance ¹	
	Beta ²	P	Beta ²	P
Play-fight	0.38 ± 0.12	0.002	15.50 ± 28.05	0.580
Wing flap	0.02 ± 0.03	0.516	17.23 ± 9.46	0.069
Jump	0.03 ± 0.06	0.700	81.10 ± 15.36	< 0.001
Run	-0.01 ± 0.07	0.877	122.83 ± 16.86	< 0.001
Ground-scratch	0.46 ± 0.22	0.034	29.45 ± 39.47	0.456
Vertical wing shake	0.22 ± 0.07	0.002	-43.88 ± 13.53	0.001
Sum of observed behaviours	0.06 ± 0.03	0.026	33.02 ± 5.89	< 0.001

¹Space allowance (m²/bird) regressed against environmental complexity, ²Beta (mean±SE)

been stimulated by increased environmental complexity although an association was only detected for play-fighting. This proposal is supported by our finding that, in the same flocks at the same age, we found fewer birds with walking difficulties in flocks with greater environmental complexity (BenSassi et al., 2019a), as expected if playful behaviour enhanced the development of the skeletomuscular system and counteracted the pre-slaughter decline in mobility otherwise typically observed in broilers (e.g. Norring et al., 2019; Thorp and Duff, 1988; Vasdal et al., 2019). Contrary to our results, Liu et al. (2020) did not detect higher levels of play in undisturbed chickens living in an environment with versus without a variety of enrichments, suggesting that differences in the types of provisions incorporated into the environment influence levels of play rather than solely the number of provisions. Also, the difference in outcomes may have arisen because the study of Liu et al. (2020) was conducted in small pens whereas we observed large flocks under commercial conditions. As our observations were performed on undisturbed birds, and not in association with stressful events, it is reasonable to interpret the higher levels of play-fighting with increased environmental complexity as indicating higher levels of positive affect associated with an excited but relaxed state and good physiological balance (Ahloy-Dallaire et al., 2018; Špinková et al., 2001).

Increased ground-scratching with greater environmental complexity could have resulted from a generally more stimulating environment and associated positive anticipation (Zimmerman et al., 2011) leading to curiosity-based inquisitive exploration. This finding, and that for vertical wing shaking, may have also been related to the provision of additional substrate materials, such as peat or extra wood shavings, which can directly stimulate substrate-oriented behaviours (Petherick and Duncan, 1989; Olsson and Keeling, 2005; Vas et al., 2020). Furthermore, higher levels of ground-scratching and vertical wing shaking may have been promoted by proximity to structures offering cover in the more complex environments, as observed by Somporn et al. (2019), thereby promoting a greater sense of security to engage in these vulnerable, ground-oriented activities. At the flock level, vertical wing shaking was correlated with ground-scratching but not with the other observed behaviours. Worm-running was quite rare, being observed in only two out of thirty flocks, but in both these flocks, the observed levels of ground-scratching and vertical wing shaking were above the median for the whole sample, and in one flock, above the upper quartile. The co-occurrence of these behaviours suggests that these litter-oriented behaviours were indirectly associated as all were stimulated by provision of additional litter materials.

Across species, several studies have reported improved welfare outcomes associated with greater environmental complexity. Laboratory rats had higher welfare when given multiple types of environmental provisions simultaneously compared with multiple copies of a single type (Abou-Ismaïl and Mendl, 2016), supporting the view that higher

Fig. 4. Association between space allowance (m²/bird) and occurrence of (a) jumps and (b) runs (values predicted from the model).

Fig. 5. Association between environmental complexity (number of enrichment types) and occurrence of (a) ground-scratches and (b) vertical wing shakes (values predicted from the model).

levels of environmental complexity per se can have beneficial effects on animal welfare. In pigs, Guy et al. (2013) reported that providing multiple types of environmental provisions had an additive effect on the animals' behaviour. Although Ocepek et al. (2020) found equivalent welfare benefits from providing pigs with peat for rooting as from providing peat plus two additional rooting materials, providing all three together was better than providing either of the other materials alone and all three individually were better than none. Furthermore, in both laboratory mice and humans, providing exercise-stimulating enrichments plus cognition-stimulating enrichments is reported to have additive benefits for brain function over providing either individually, which are better than providing no enrichments (Dhir et al., 2021; Fabel et al., 2009). In chickens, while different provisions have varied in their individual effects on different welfare indicators (e.g. Bach et al., 2019; Pedersen et al., 2020; Tahamtani et al., 2018a, 2018b, 2020), access to multiple types of litter and perches simultaneously shortened the duration of tonic immobility, reduced heterophil/lymphocyte ratios, boosted natural antibody concentrations, and increased exploitation of novel food by comparison with access to only a single type of litter and perch (Nazar et al., 2022). These studies, together with the present findings, suggest that welfare benefits from environmental complexity can be maximised by providing multiple types of enrichments targeting different biological functions.

4.2. Associations with space allowance

In the case of space allowance, our hypothesis was supported by the results on jumping, running and the sum of observed behaviours, although the results for vertical wing shakes gave contrary results. We observed higher levels of jumping and running, two space-consuming behaviours co-occurring in our sample population, with increasing space per bird over and above that accounted for when providing greater environmental complexity. However, this was not the case for the two other analysed play behaviours, play-fighting (sparring) and wing flapping. This might be because birds can direct play-fights, with or without wing flaps, to several nearby birds in rapid succession without long runs in between each play-fight event. At higher stocking densities, we would expect such encounters to occur at higher rates, counteracting the effect of less space being available for more space-demanding jumps and runs often performed prior to play-fights. The space allowances in the current study ranged from 0.058 to 0.076 m²/bird, corresponding to densities ranging from 18.1 to 29.6 kg/m², on the day of observation. In Hall (2001), density on the day of slaughter (34 vs 40 kg/m²) was not related to the frequencies of sparring and wing flapping behaviour at 23 or 37 days either. Rayner et al. (2020) also detected no difference between levels of these behaviours among undisturbed broilers of a slower-growing strain stocked at planned final densities of 30 vs 34 kg/m².

Based on our findings, jumping and running were triggered more by higher space allowances than by increased environmental complexity. A

higher space allowance meant that, as birds moved spontaneously within the house, there were more moments when areas of free space could temporarily open up triggering playful locomotion (Baxter et al., 2019, 2020; Liu et al., 2020; Rayner et al., 2020) and, thus, more opportunities for longer jumps and runs unimpeded by conspecifics in the path of movement. It is also possible that having more space available during early life led to greater physical exercise during ontogeny, contributing to better physiological preparedness, including stronger bones and muscles and a more sound cardiovascular system (Bessei, 2006; Thorp and Duff, 1988), for intense playful jumping and running at the age when our observations were conducted. While detecting a clear link between leg problems and behavioural activity has proved elusive (Sherlock et al., 2010; Vasdál et al., 2019), lower densities have been associated with a lower prevalence of leg problems or walking difficulties (BenSassi et al., 2019a; Dawkins et al., 2004; Hall, 2001; Sørensen et al., 2000), longer distances moved (Estevez et al., 1997; Leone et al., 2007; Leone and Estevez, 2008; Lewis and Hurnik, 1990), and higher frequencies of locomotion (Bach et al., 2019) or walking (Hall, 2001). Nevertheless, it should be noted that severe leg problems, identified as gait score 4 and 5 in the Bristol system (Kestin et al., 1992) or as severe walking difficulties during transect walks (BenSassi et al., 2019a), are found at relatively low levels in commercial flocks around four-weeks age (BenSassi et al., 2019a; Kestin et al., 1992; Tahamtani et al., 2018a) and birds with such problems are different from those at the other end of spectrum observed performing highly energetic playful behaviours in the same flock. Therefore, it remains unclear whether leg problems and playful behaviour are causally related.

Similarly to the findings of Hall (2001), ground-scratching was observed at comparable frequencies across flocks varying in density. This is not surprising, as this behaviour is primarily influenced by the litter quality (Petherick and Duncan, 1989; Vas et al., 2020). Regarding dustbathing, this behaviour occurs in a long sequence of elements that can take up to 75 min to complete but is terminated earlier when disturbed (Guinebretière et al., 2014). We expected more disturbance and, hence, termination of dustbathing in denser flocks (Dawkins et al., 2004; Hall, 2001) and therefore predicted that we would observe more dustbathing at lower densities. On the contrary, less dustbathing behaviour was observed at lower densities. This finding could be related to the social environment, as dustbathing is hypothesized to be socially facilitated (Duncan et al., 1998), and the presence of more birds dustbathing nearby at higher densities may trigger dustbathing by more other birds in the vicinity. Given that dustbathing is a vulnerable behaviour performed on the ground, birds may experience a greater sense of security (safety in numbers) to engage in dustbathing at higher densities. In addition, the observed higher levels of jumping and running in flocks with more space may have disrupted long bouts of dustbathing (Guinebretière et al., 2014), resulting in fewer observations of vertical wing shaking in less dense flocks.

4.3. Limitations

With our direct observation method, we aimed to create as minimal disturbance as possible and only began observations after chickens settled after the initial arousal caused by our entry into the house. Nevertheless, we cannot be sure that the birds observed two transects across from our location were completely undisturbed by our presence in the house. The total number of birds in a patch could be high (estimated mean \pm SE, 51 \pm 0.2 birds/patch), so it was not practical to count the total number. In the future, it may be possible to capture the actual totals using overhead cameras, and to determine the number of birds performing each behaviour using machine learning, allowing for a more refined estimate of the frequency of each behaviour than was possible through direct observation. There was variation across flocks in the quantity, dispersion, and timing of providing different environmental supplements but exploring associations with these factors would have required a larger sample of flocks, and more precise information from

the farmers, than was available for this study. We discovered that space allocation and number of environmental provisions were correlated in our sample and, therefore, we regressed the space on number of provisions and used the space residuals to create unrelated variables. It is possible that space allowance associations with behaviour would differ if environmental complexity was unrelated to stocking density. Another consideration is age, as our observations were conducted at the age of 28 days (range: 26–31 days). It is likely that the associations that we found between space allowance and behaviour would be more pronounced at older ages when space is more limited and birds may face more health problems, and at younger ages, when play is more prevalent (e.g. Liu et al., 2020). The findings of this study are limited to the fast-growing hybrid used, and may differ in slower-growing hybrids (e.g. Rayner et al., 2020). The chickens in this study were kept at an average slaughter-age density of 32.1 kg/m² (23.4 kg/m² when visited), which is lower than in the European Union where a maximum density of 42 kg/m² is permitted if mortality is repeatedly low (EC, 2007).

5. Conclusions

We investigated the prevalence of elements of play, inquisitive exploration, and comfort behaviour (worm-run, play-fight, wing flap, jump, run, ground-scratch and vertical wing shake) as indicators of positive affective states in chickens. We found that, when summed together, these behaviours were performed spontaneously by an estimated average of 1% of birds during daytime observed in scans of undisturbed 28-day-old fast-growing chickens in commercial flocks. Thus, these were relatively rare behaviours comprising only a small proportion of the behavioural time budget. Nevertheless, all of the behaviours except wing flapping and worm-running were positively associated with either number of environmental enrichments provided or space allocation, suggesting that their assessment in the context of spontaneous performance by undisturbed birds can contribute to integrative measures of better animal welfare and quality of life in broiler chickens. The applied transect method for sampling behaviour was feasible for practical, direct scanning of large numbers of birds within commercial flocks for the occurrence of noticeable but relatively rare behaviours. This method can be especially useful when individual tracking of animals or use of video recordings is not possible, and when it is necessary to collect data from a large sample of animals within a limited time period (e.g. to accommodate farmers' busy work schedules and to avoid observer fatigue when travelling long distances to conduct farm visits). We conclude that both plentiful space allowance and environmental heterogeneity (environmental complexity) are relevant features of the physical environment of production animals that stimulate hedonically positive states and thereby contribute to better quality of life.

Ethical perspectives

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest in the research. The procedures did not involve any handling of animals, and the observed animals were in existing commercial flocks managed according to typical commercial routines. Therefore, according to Norwegian regulations, no ethical permission was required.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

The study was funded by The Research Council of Norway (project 258881) for the European Union Animal Health and Welfare (ANIHWA) ERA-Net Initiative (<https://www.anihwa-submission-era.net/imdbdata>)

project "Integrated EU mobile broiler data – Optimising broiler chicken management, health & welfare through use of integrated EU data". The authors are grateful to the farmers who participated in the research and to Nortura for providing flock data.

Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.applanim.2023.105901](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2023.105901).

References

- Abou-Ismaïl, U.A., Mendl, M.T., 2016. The effects of enrichment novelty versus complexity in cages of group-housed rats (*Rattus norvegicus*). *Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci.* 180, 130–139. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2016.04.014>.
- Ahloy-Dallaire, J., Espinosa, J., Mason, G., 2018. Play and optimal welfare: Does play indicate the presence of positive affective states. *Behav. Process.* 156, 3–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.beproc.2017.11.011>.
- Anderson, M.G., Campbell, A.M., Crump, A., Arnott, G., Newberry, R.C., Jacobs, L., 2021. Effect of environmental complexity and stocking density on fear and anxiety in broiler chickens. *Animals* 11, 2383. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani11082383>.
- Aviagen, 2022. Ross 308/308 FF Broiler: Performance Objectives. Aviagen Publication 0822-AVNR-157. Available at: https://eu.aviagen.com/assets/Tech_Center/Ross_Broiler/Ross308-BroilerPerformanceObjectives2022-EN.pdf.
- Bach, M.H., Tahamtani, F.M., Pedersen, I.J., Riber, A.B., 2019. Effects of environmental complexity on behaviour in fast-growing broiler chickens. *Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci.* 219, 104840. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2019.104840>.
- Bailie, C.L., Ball, M.E.E., O'Connell, N.E., 2013. Influence of the provision of natural light and straw bales on activity levels and leg health in commercial broiler chickens. *Animal* 7, 618–626. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1751731112002108>.
- Baxter, M., Bailie, C.L., O'Connell, N.E., 2019. Play behaviour, fear responses and activity levels in commercial broiler chickens provided with preferred environmental enrichments. *Animal* 13, 171–179. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1751731118001118>.
- Baxter, M., Richmond, A., Lavery, U., O'Connell, N.E., 2020. Investigating optimal levels of platform perch provision for windowed broiler housing. *Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci.* 225, 104967. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2020.104967>.
- Baxter, M., Richmond, A., Lavery, U., O'Connell, N.E., 2021. A comparison of fast growing broiler chickens with a slower-growing breed type reared on Higher Welfare commercial farms. *PLoS ONE* 16, e0259333. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0259333>.
- BenSassi, N., Averós, X., Estevez, I., 2018. The potential of the transect method for early detection of welfare problems in broiler chickens. *Poult. Sci.* 0, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.3382/ps/pey374>.
- BenSassi, N., Vas, J., Vasdal, G., Averós, X., Estévez, I., Newberry, R.C., 2019a. On-farm broiler chicken welfare assessment using transect sampling reflects environmental inputs and production outcomes. *PLoS One* 14, e0214070. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0214070>.
- BenSassi, N., Averós, X., Estevez, I., 2019b. Broiler chickens on-farm welfare assessment: estimating the robustness of the transect sampling method. *Front. Vet. Sci.* 6, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fvets.2019.00236>.
- Bergmann, S., Schwarzer, A., Wilutzky, K., Louton, H., Bachmeier, J., Schmidt, P., Erhad, M., Rauch, E., 2017. Behavior as welfare indicator for the rearing of broilers in an enriched husbandry environment—a field study. *J. Vet. Behav.* 19, 90–101. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jveb.2017.03.003>.
- de Jong, I.C., Blaauw, X.E., van der Eijk, J.A.J., Souza da Silva, C., van Krimpen, M.M., Molenaar, R., van den Brand, H., 2021. Providing environmental enrichments affects activity and performance, but not leg health in fast- and slower-growing broiler chickens. *Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci.* 241, 105375. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2021.105375>.
- Kestin, S.C., Knowles, T.G., Tinch, A.E., Gregory, N.G., 1992. Prevalence of leg weakness in broiler chickens and its relationship with genotype. *Vet. Rec.* 131, 190–194. <https://doi.org/10.1136/vr.131.9.190>.
- Knowles, T.G., Broom, D.M., 1990. Limb bone strength and movement in laying hens from different housing systems. *Vet. Rec.* 126, 354–356. <https://doi.org/10.1136/vr.126.15.354>.
- Lawrence, A.B., Vigors, B., Sandøe, P., 2019. What is so positive about positive animal welfare?—a critical review of the literature. *Animals* 9, 783. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani9100783>.
- Leone, E.H., Estevez, I., 2008. Use of space in the domestic fowl: separating the effects of enclosure size, group size and density. *Anim. Behav.* 76, 1673–1682. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anbehav.2008.08.004>.
- Leone, E.H., Estevez, I., Christman, M.C., 2007. Environmental complexity and group size: immediate effects on use of space by domestic fowl. *Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci.* 102, 39–52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2006.03.004>.
- Lewis, N.J., Hurnik, J.F., 1990. Locomotion of broiler chickens in floor pens. *Poult. Sci.* 69, 1087–1093. <https://doi.org/10.3382/ps.0691087>.
- R Core Team, 2022. R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. <https://www.R-project.org/>.
- Berlyne, D.E., 1960. Conflict, arousal, and curiosity. New York, NY, US: McGraw-Hill Book Company. McGraw-Hill Book Company, New York, NY, US. <https://doi.org/10.1037/11164-000>.
- Bessei, W., 2006. Welfare of broilers: a review. *Worlds Poult. Sci. J.* 62, 455–466. <https://doi.org/10.1079/WPS2005108>.
- Bizeray, D., Estevez, I., Lettierier, C., Faure, J.M., 2002. Influence of increased environmental complexity on leg condition, performance, and level of fearfulness in broilers. *Poult. Sci.* 81, 767–773. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ps/81.6.767>.
- Boissy, A., Manteuffel, G., Jensen, M.B., Moe, R.O., Spruijt, B., Keeling, L.J., Winckler, C., Forkman, B., Dimitrov, I., Langbein, J., Bakken, M., Veissier, I., Aubert, A., 2007. Assessment of positive emotions in animals to improve their welfare. *Physiol. Behav.* 92, 375–397. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physbeh.2007.02.003>.
- Burghardt, G.M., 2014. A brief glimpse at the long evolutionary history of play. *Anim. Behav. Cogn.* 1, 90–98. <https://doi.org/10.12966/abc.05.01.2014>.
- Cloutier, S., Newberry, R.C., Honda, K., 2004. Comparison of social ranks based on worm-running and aggressive behaviour in young domestic fowl. *Behav. Process.* 65, 79–86. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.beproc.2003.07.001>.
- Dawkins, M.S., Donnelly, C.A., Jones, T.A., 2004. Chicken welfare is influenced more by housing conditions than by stocking density. *Nature* 427, 342–344. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature02226>.
- Dennis, R.L., Newberry, R.C., Cheng, H.-W., Estevez, I., 2008. Appearance matters: artificial marking alters aggression and stress. *Poult. Sci.* 87, 1939–1946. <https://doi.org/10.3382/ps.2007-00311>.
- Dhir, S., Teo, W.P., Chamberlain, S.R., Tyler, K., Yücel, M., Segrave, R.A., 2021. The effects of combined physical and cognitive training on inhibitory control: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Neurosci. Biobehav. Rev.* 128, 735–748. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neubiorev.2021.07.008>.
- Duncan, I.J.H., Widowski, T.M., Malleau, A.E., Lindberg, A.C., Petherick, J.C., 1998. External factors and causation of dustbathing in domestic hens. *Behav. Process.* 43, 219–228. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0376-6357\(98\)00017-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0376-6357(98)00017-5).
- Estevez, I., Newberry, R., Arias de Reyna, L., 1997. Broiler chickens: a tolerant social system? *Etologia* 5, 19–29.
- European Commission, 2007. Council Directive 2007/43/EC of 28 June 2007 laying down minimum rules for the protection of chickens kept for meat production. *J. Eur. Union* 19–28.
- Fabel, K., Wolf, S.A., Ehninger, D., Babu, H., Leal-Galicia, P., Kempermann, G., 2009. Additive effects of physical exercise and environmental enrichment on adult hippocampal neurogenesis in mice. *Front. Neurosci.* 3, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnro.2009.0002.2009>.
- FAWC, 2009. Farm Animal Welfare in Great Britain: Past, Present and Future. London. Fortomaris, P., Arsenos, G., Tserveni-Gousi, A., Yannakopoulos, A., 2007. Performance and behaviour of broiler chickens as affected by the housing system. *Arch. für Geflügelkd.* 71, 97–104.
- Guinebretière, M., Beyer, H., Arnould, C., Michel, V., 2014. The choice of litter material to promote pecking, scratching and dustbathing behaviours in laying hens housed in furnished cages. *Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci.* 155, 56–65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2014.02.013>.
- Guy, J.H., Meads, Z.A., Shiel, R.S., Edwards, S.A., 2013. The effect of combining different environmental enrichment materials on enrichment use by growing pigs. *Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci.* 144, 102–107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2013.01.006>.
- Hall, A.L., 2001. The effect of stocking density on the welfare and behaviour of broiler chickens reared commercially. *Anim. Welf.* 10, 23–40.
- Himmler, B.T., Pellis, S.M., Kolb, B., 2013. Juvenile play experience primes neurons in the medial prefrontal cortex to be more responsive to later experiences. *Neurosci. Lett.* 556, 42–45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neulet.2013.09.061>.
- Holt, R.V., Vas, J., Vasdal, G., Newberry, R.C., 2023. A buffet of litters - broiler chickens behave differently according to litter type and freshness. *Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci.* 260, 105856. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2023.105856>.
- Jones, P.J., Tahamtani, F.M., Pedersen, I.J., Niemi, J.K., Riber, A.B., 2020. The productivity and financial impacts of eight types of environmental enrichment for broiler chickens. *Animals* 10, 378. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani10030378>.
- de Jong, I.C., Wolthuis-Fillerup, M., van Reenen, C.G., 2007. Strength of preference for dustbathing and foraging substrates in laying hens. *Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci.* 104, 24–36. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2006.04.027>.
- Liu, Z., Torrey, S., Newberry, R.C., Widowski, T., 2020. Play behaviour reduced by environmental enrichment in fast-growing broiler chickens. *Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci.* 232, 105098. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2020.105098>.
- Lundén, G., Oscarsson, R., Hedlund, L., Gjøen, J., Jensen, P., 2022. Play ontogeny in young chickens is affected by domestication and early stress. *Sci. Rep.* 12, 13576. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-17617-x>.
- Marchewka, J., Watanabe, T.T.N., Ferrante, V., Estevez, I., 2013. Welfare assessment in broiler farms: transect walks versus individual scoring. *Poult. Sci.* 92, 2588–2599. <https://doi.org/10.3382/ps.2013-03229>.
- Marchewka, J., Estevez, I., Vezzoli, G., Ferrante, V., Makagon, M.M., 2015. The transect method: a novel approach to on-farm welfare assessment of commercial turkeys. *Poult. Sci.* 94, 7–16. <https://doi.org/10.3382/ps/peu026>.
- McGrath, N., Dunlop, R., Dwyer, C., Burman, O., Phillips, C.J.C., 2017. Hens vary their vocal repertoire and structure when anticipating different types of reward. *Anim. Behav.* 130, 79–96. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anbehav.2017.05.025>.
- McMillan, F.D., 2000. Quality of life in animals. *J. Am. Vet. Assoc.* 216, 1904–1910. <https://doi.org/10.2460/javma.2000.216.1904>.
- Meyer, M.M., Johnson, A.K., Bobeck, E.A., 2020. Development and validation of broiler welfare assessment methods for research and on-farm audits. *J. Appl. Anim. Welf. Sci.* 23, 433–446. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10888705.2019.1678039>.
- Nazar, F.N., Skånberg, L., McCrea, K., Keeling, L.J., 2022. Increasing environmental complexity by providing different types of litter and perches during early rearing boosts coping abilities in domestic fowl chicks. *Animals* 12, 1969. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani12151969>.

- Newberry, R.C., 1995. Environmental enrichment: Increasing the biological relevance of captive environments. *Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci.* 44, 229–243. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1591\(95\)00616-Z](https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-1591(95)00616-Z).
- Nicol, C.J., 1987. Behavioural responses of laying hens following a period of spatial restriction. *Anim. Behav.* 35, 1709–1719. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0003-3472\(87\)80063-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0003-3472(87)80063-5).
- Nørgaard-Nielsen, G., 1990. Bone strength of laying hens kept in an alternative system, compared with hens in cages and on deep-litter. *Br. Poult. Sci.* 31, 81–89. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00071669008417233>.
- Norring, M., Valros, A., Valaja, J., Sihvo, H., Immonen, K., Puolanne, E., 2019. Wooden breast myopathy links with poorer gait in broiler chickens. *Animal* 13, 1690–1695. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1751731118003270>.
- Ocepek, M., Newberry, R.C., Andersen, I.L., 2020. Which types of rooting material give weaner pigs most pleasure. *Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci.* 231, 105070. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2020.105070>.
- Olsson, I.A.S., Keeling, L.J., 2005. Why in earth? Dustbathing behaviour in jungle and domestic fowl reviewed from a Tinbergian and animal welfare perspective. *Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci.* 93, 259–282. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2004.11.018>.
- Pedersen, I.J., Tahamtani, F.M., Forkman, B., Young, J.F., Poulsen, H.D., Riber, A.B., 2020. Effects of environmental enrichment on health and bone characteristics of fast growing broiler chickens. *Poult. Sci.* 99, 1946–1955. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2019.11.061>.
- Petherick, J.C., Duncan, I.J.H., 1989. Behaviour of young domestic fowl directed towards different substrates. *Br. Poult. Sci.* 30, 229–238. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00071668908417143>.
- Rayner, A.C., Newberry, R.C., Vas, J., Mullan, S., 2020. Slow-growing broilers are healthier and express more behavioural indicators of positive welfare. *Sci. Rep.* 10, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-72198-x>.
- Riber, A.B., van de Weerd, H.A., de Jong, I.C., Steinfeldt, S., 2018. Review of environmental enrichment for broiler chickens. *Poult. Sci.* 97, 378–396. <https://doi.org/10.3382/ps/pex344>.
- Sherlock, L., Demmers, T., Goodship, A., McCarthy, I., Wathes, C.M., 2010. The relationship between physical activity and leg health in the broiler chicken. *Br. Poult. Sci.* 51, 22–30. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00071660903460637>.
- Shields, S.J., Garner, J.P., Mench, J.A., 2004. Dustbathing by broiler chickens: a comparison of preference for four different substrates. *Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci.* 87, 69–82. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2004.01.003>.
- Siviy, S.M., Harrison, K.A., McGregor, I.S., 2006. Fear, risk assessment, and playfulness in the juvenile rat. *Behav. Neurosci.* 120, 49–59. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0735-7044.120.1.49>.
- Sompam, P., Damnoensakunchai, M., Sutthiluk, W., 2019. Effects of vertical panel on the behavior of Thai Native Chicken hens paired with cocks kept in bamboo chicken coops. *Thai J. Agric. Sci.* 52 (4), 232–242. <https://li01.tci-thaijo.org/index.php/TJAS/article/view/246048/168203>.
- Sørensen, P., Su, G., Kestin, S.C., 2000. Effects of age and stocking density on leg weakness in broiler chickens. *Poult. Sci.* 79, 864–870. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ps/79.6.864>.
- Špinka, M., Newberry, R.C., Bekoff, M., 2001. Mammalian play: training for the unexpected. *Quarterly Rev. Biol.* 76, 141–168. <https://doi.org/10.1086/393866>.
- Tahamtani, F.M., Hinrichsen, L.K., Riber, A.B., 2018a. Welfare assessment of conventional and organic broilers in Denmark, with emphasis on leg health. *Vet. Rec.* 183, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1136/vr.104817>.
- Tahamtani, F.M., Pedersen, I.J., Toinon, C., Riber, A.B., 2018b. Effects of environmental complexity on fearfulness and learning ability in fast growing broiler chickens. *Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci.* 207, 49–56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2018.04.005>.
- Tahamtani, F.M., Pedersen, I.J., Riber, A.B., 2020. Effects of environmental complexity on welfare indicators of fast-growing broiler chickens. *Poult. Sci.* 99, 21–29. <https://doi.org/10.3382/ps/pez510>.
- Thorp, B.H., Duff, S.R.L., 1988. Effect of exercise on the vascular pattern in the bone extremities of broiler fowl. *Res. Vet. Sci.* 45, 72–77. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0034-5288\(18\)30897-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0034-5288(18)30897-X).
- van Liere, D.W., 1992. Dustbathing as related to proximal and distal feather lipids in laying hens. *Behav. Process.* 26, 177–188. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0376-6357\(92\)90012-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0376-6357(92)90012-3).
- van Liere, D.W., 1991. Function and organization of dustbathing in laying hens. University of Wageningen, Wageningen, NL.
- Vanderschuren, L.J.M., Niesink, R.J.M., Spuijnt, B.M., van Ree, J.M., 1995. Influence of environmental factors on social play behavior of juvenile rats. *Physiol. Behav.* 58, 119–123. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0031-9384\(94\)00385-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0031-9384(94)00385-1).
- Vas, J., BenSassi, N., Vasdal, G., Newberry, R.C., 2020. Rewarding memories? Behaviour of broiler chickens towards peat in flocks with and without previous exposure to peat. *Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci.* 232. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2020.105129>.
- Vasdal, G., Vas, J., Newberry, R.C., Moe, R.O., 2019. Effects of environmental enrichment on activity and lameness in commercial broiler production. *J. Appl. Anim. Welf. Sci.* 22, 197–205. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10888705.2018.1456339>.
- Vestergaard, K.S., Sanotra, G.S., 1999. Relationships between leg disorders and changes in the behaviour of broiler chickens. *Vet. Rec.* 144, 205–210. <https://doi.org/10.1136/vr.144.8.205>.
- Vezzoli, G., Mullens, B.A., Mench, J.A., 2015. Dustbathing behavior: do ectoparasites matter. *Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci.* 169, 93–99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applanim.2015.06.001>.
- Webb, L.E., Veenhoven, R., Harfeld, J.L., Jensen, M.B., 2019. What is animal happiness? *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci.* 1438, 62–76. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nyas.13983>.
- Widowski, T.M., Duncan, I.J.H., 2000. Working for a dustbath: are hens increasing pleasure rather than reducing suffering. *Appl. Anim. Behav. Sci.* 68, 39–53. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591\(00\)00088-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0168-1591(00)00088-5).
- Zimmerman, P.H., Buijs, S.A.F., Bolhuis, J.E., Keeling, L.J., 2011. Behaviour of domestic fowl in anticipation of positive and negative stimuli. *Anim. Behav.* 81, 569–577. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anbehav.2010.11.028>.